

Article Title: Accuracy of implant placement after preoperative planning using Blueprint software in inlay and onlay reverse total shoulder arthroplasty systems: a cadaver study

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<https://medicine.utah.edu/orthopaedics/research/labs/harold-dunn/groups/henninger>

The repository contains a data release in support of the published manuscript. It includes CT image stacks (*.nii) of cadaver specimens before preparation ('clean') and after implant removal ('final'), as well as post-processed data describing the differences between pre-operative planning and the performed surgery (*.xlsx). The CT data can be read with freeware like 3D Slicer. The included spreadsheet is a modified version of that hosted with the manuscript itself (described below).

Note that no data on implant surfaces or direct pre-operative planning outputs from the Stryker Blueprint software are provided to prevent the release of any potential proprietary information.

Anatomic surfaces of the scapulae and humeri, and labeled anatomic landmarks from those surfaces, can be found in: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14590061>

These specimens were also experimentally tested in a study of reverse total shoulder arthroplasty: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38036254/>

Zitnay JL, Tashjian RZ, Walch G, Chalmers PN, Joyce CD, Henninger HB. Inlay vs. onlay humeral components in reverse total shoulder arthroplasty: a biorobotic shoulder simulator study. *J Shoulder Elbow Surg.* 2024 Jun;33(6):1377-1386. doi: 10.1016/j.jse.2023.10.015. PMCID: PMC11098709.

Specific to the contents of this repository:

1. Naming convention:
 - a. Group_sex_age_side_CTstatus
 - b. E.g., Inlay_F_51_R_clean_CT – an **Inlay** implant tested in a **Female** specimen, age **51** years, **Right** side, where the CT image stack is **prior to preparation**
2. Database contents
 - a. **Folders:** N=40 folders containing CT image data of the cadavers in (*.nii) format. There are two folders per specimen: 1 pre-preparation, 1 after implant removal. There are 10 specimens per group for each of the Inlay and Onlay implant systems.
 - b. **SUPPLEMENT_rTSA_Accuracy_260520.xlsx** – a modified version of the post-processed data hosted with the manuscript itself, now clarifying naming conventions for specimens of the same age (e.g., ‘a’ vs. ‘b’), correcting the age in one specimen (incorrectly labeled 32 years, now 71 years), addition of humeral implant parameters, and cross-referenced naming to prior data releases.

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